

USE OF MOBILE TECHNOLOGY IN UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES: A RECENT TREND

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Paper Received On: 22 Jan 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 16 Feb 2024

Released On: 01 March 2024

Abstract

We are living in age of Information technology. Mobile became most important device in the field of Information technology. It became necessary part of human life. In university libraries, mobile also became essential instrument for library users as most of university libraries are providing information and document delivery through SMS services, e-mail services, whatsapp service in users mobile device. Similarly, university libraries have social media e.g., face book, Instragram, twitter etc. accounts which can be used in mobile device. Also, most of university libraries using mobile technology to provide library users with access to digital resources such as e-books, e-journals, digital magazines, and other digital journals. University libraries are using mobile technology to provide library users with access to real time information about library services, such as hours of operation and upcoming events. In real sense the appeal of mobile phones going beyond the fact that users no longer need the library to get information that does not require time investment if it is available outside the library with one click to make things accessible in the library and anywhere any time. No doubt implementation of mobile technology in university libraries will help to build good relationship and will be able to provide better services especially to remote area users. This article discusses the use and applications o mobile technology in university libraries, mobile applications and university library services using mobile technology.

Keywords: *ICT, University Library, Mobile technology, Accessibility through mobile, SMS, Document delivery. Information technology. Remote area users.*

The use of mobile technology in library may be stated as follows

1. Library services through mobile Technology

1. Alert or notification services: Libraries are providing instant messages and multimedia messages warning services about latest arrivals, deadlines, unpaid fines, return notices, renewals and other important matters related to libraries to their users. These are generated by using integrated library management software.
2. Database browsing services: Users can easily checkup the status of available resources in the OPAC library. Like OCLC AS Word Catalog mobile application.
3. Learning Services: Mobile technology is a ideal platform for delivering learning services. With advances in mobile technology such as Smartphone, laptops and tablets users can access educational content resources from anywhere at any time. This mobile technology can also be used to deliver personalized learning experiences such as micro learning, and adaptive learning. Mobile technology also provides virtual collaboration and communication with other learners, teachers, students and research scholars.
4. Access to e-resources: Most of the library e-resources are now available to access through mobile device. Most of university library websites have been optimized for mobile devices so that users can search brows and access e-resources on the goggle or on other search engines. The university libraries offer apps that allow users to search their catalog and access digital documents. Besides these many e-book publishers have mobile applications that allow users to read e-books on their devices.
5. Personal Space: At personal mode users can create their own profiles manage their online resources categorize their resources, check the product loaned to their account. payment details, manage their users and send requests and all other necessary things to access.
6. Reference Services: University libraries are also providing reference services to their users through their mobile devices. These can be search library catalog, ask questions of librarians, access library digital collections and receive alert notice about library events.
7. Document Delivery Services: University libraries through document delivery services making easy for users to access and manage documents such as research papers, news articles and other legal documents. Mobile document delivery services provide wide range of information and documents like books journals annual reports and other digital contents which could be in form of pdf, html and e-book.
8. My library on Mobile Device: University my library service is a comprehensive collection of library resources and services designed to fulfill educational and recreational needs of users. Technology based services are also provided on my library services e.g., set alerts reminders, updates on new books, online renew, renewal request, due dates reminder, delay

notification, arrival request service new title notification service news and event reminder service.

2. Skill requirements: Libraries acquire following skills to implement mobile services in their libraries:

1. Familiar with Smartphone screens and applications.
2. Let`s familiarize ourselves with device software used in various mobile devices.
3. Knowledge of library homepage creation, OPAC, content optimized for mobile and virtual tours.
4. Ability to work intelligently with third party clients.
5. Knowledge about mobile device hardware and software. Overview of interacting with library users through a smart phone application.

3. Essential Requirements for Implementation of Mobile based Services in University libraries:

1. Planning a carefully designed plan for implementation of mobile services in libraries. Learning is planned and practical is performed through mobile devices.
2. A good mobile application development platform is needed to develop the library services which may include a cross plate form mobile app development plate form such as React Native, Xamarin, Flutter, or a native mobile app development plate form such as iOS SDK, Android etc.
3. Acquisition of necessary hardware and software after market research.
4. An active internet connection.
5. Good database to collect all library data.
6. Updates library websites, OPAC and databases to be mobile.
7. A security system is required to ensure that all library data are safe and protected from unauthorized access.
8. A physical and virtual environment is necessary for using mobile services.
9. Provision of payment gateway is necessary to enable users to make payments for library services.

4. Advances of Mobile technology in Libraries:

1. Mobile Technology is Time saving, as users do not need to travel.
2. It is user friendly: Most of university library users uses mobile device and have easy access to online information provided by the university library. Mobile technology provides easy-

to-use feature to its users. Thus, users can easily access online information provided by their university libraries using user friendly features of mobile devices.

3. **Enhanced Engagement:** University Libraries can use mobile technology to engage patrons through social media, apps and text messages allowing them to connect with the university library in new and distinct ways.
4. **User Participation:** University libraries can add new features by enriching OPAC facility to allow users to upload users' images and notes.
5. **Quick feedback:** Through mobile technology users can give quick feedback and get quick response related to library services.
6. **Increased Collaboration:** Mobile technology makes it easier for library staff to collaborate on projects and share information.
5. **Attitude of Users towards use of Mobile Technology in University Libraries:** A survey is performed by me about attitude of PG Students and Research scholars towards use of mobile technology in selected university libraries. The findings of study showed that maximum number of users possess' Positive attitude towards use of mobile device in university libraries. Only few users showed negative attitude who were no aware of use of online library information services. The study suggests to organize training programs, webinars, seminars and workshops to develop information literacy skills and awareness about use of library and information services mainly in university libraries.

6. Limitations / Barriers:

1. **Content ownership Licensing and Digital rights:** Due to overflow of informant on internet it became difficult for librarians to maintain copyright and ownership of digital contents.
2. **High cost to implement mobile library services.**
3. **Limited mobile device memory.**
4. **Limited screen size of mobile devices.**
5. **Less bandwidth speeds.**
6. **Lack of trained staff.**
7. **Limited accessibility.**
8. **User Education:** Users may be less aware of how to access and use library resources.
9. **Security and Privacy;** Mobile devices may be vulnerable to security risks such viruses, malware and hacking which can put both library data and users' information at risk.
10. **Limited battery life.** The users can't access library services when their mobile device runs out of power.

11. Common Things: Libraries needed to develop tools and techniques to such kinds of practices.
12. Inconvenience of taking printout of any document.
7. **Conclusion:** Mobile technology can be used to improve University library services in various ways. It can be used to provide access to library collection and services. Mobile technology can be used to increase efficiency of library staff. It also can be used to deliver educational programs, resources, to engage users in library activities and enhance communication and collaboration among library users and staff. Mobile technology can help university libraries to develop innovative and sustainable solutions that will help them to remain in this digital age. The main challenge in field of mobile technology in university
8. **Libraries is to maintain ownership and copyright of digital content:** Besides these limitations the use mobile technology in university library is a opportunity to library users such as students, research scholars, teachers, professors library professionals even whole university staff. No doubt the coming age will be mobile age and mobile will perform most of computer work from anywhere at any time free from boundaries of time and place with one click and human will get all necessary things on mobile or by mobile and will feel mobile as a blessing of God in this universe.

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